

MODELLING STRESS TRANSFER IN A WOOD COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: A model has been developed for the longitudinal elastic modulus of a new structural wood composite, Scrimber. The model has been developed using a micromechanics of composites approach, and is based on the Krenchel model. The morphology of Scrimber has been studied in order to estimate the effects of strand discontinuity, strand misorientation, strand damage during pressing, and wood densification during production of the composite. The prediction of the model was within 2% of the measured modulus for a single batch of Scrimber. Similar models should be very useful for other structural wood composites.

This paper concentrates on the effect of strand discontinuity on the modulus. The strand discontinuity factor was estimated using a measured strand aspect ratio distribution, modified by strand end shape criteria, and a form of the shear-lag theory of stress transfer.

KEYWORDS: wood composites, modelling, stress transfer, modulus

INTRODUCTION

Wood composites are a class of materials which are formed by breaking down wood into smaller wood elements which are then bonded together again in a different form. A class of wood composites increasingly used for structural purposes are the "Artificial Lumber" or "Composite Lumber" materials such as Parallel Strand Lumber and Laminated Veneer Lumber, materials which have similar properties to wood itself. These have been developed to meet the demand for timber-like products at a time when the supply of large old-growth trees, which are the most suitable for sawn timber production, is steadily decreasing.

Despite the common use of the term wood composites to describe these materials, and the strong links with the polymer composites industry provided by groups like the US Forest Products Laboratory, the industry has tended to regard these materials as an exotic species of timber, rather than studying these materials as composites, an engineered material. Although a great deal of theory has developed to predict the properties of many composites, there appears to have been little serious use of such theory to predict the properties of wood composites.

A new form of "composite lumber", Scrimber, has been developed in Australia. Scrimber is produced from strands produced by passing juvenile Radiata Pine logs through a series of rolls. This splits the log in the grain direction, and produces batches of partially-connected strands called increments. The width and thickness of these strands typically varies from 1 to 10 mm, and their length typically varies from 10 to 200x the width or thickness. These are dried, coated with adhesive, and laid up into a preform. The preform is then consolidated before being compressed and cured in a radio frequency heated press. The principal direction

of the strands in the beam is close to parallel to the long direction of the Scrimber beam. Scrimber has an obvious “grain” and “grain direction”.

Scrimber is in many ways similar to a unidirectional fibre composite. The basic starting point for the prediction of the longitudinal modulus of such a composite is often the Rule of Mixtures:

$$E_c = E_f V_f + E_m V_m \quad (1)$$

where E is the modulus, V the volume fraction, and the subscripts "c", "f" and "m" refer to the composite, fibres and matrix respectively. In the derivation of this equation it is assumed that the fibres are continuous; that the fibres are perfectly aligned in the longitudinal direction; that there is perfect bonding between fibre and matrix; and that the constituents are linearly elastic for the stresses expected.

In Scrimber, as in many practical composites, the “fibres” are neither perfectly aligned nor continuous. Krenchel (Theory 1) [1] was one of the first to predict the modulus of such composites. He built on the Rule of Mixtures model, introducing two “fibre efficiency” factors. These factors (here referred to as η_o , for fibre orientation, and η_{st} , for stress transfer) allow for the effect of fibre orientation and fibre discontinuity on the composite modulus. His equation has been rewritten using the more usual terminology introduced above:

$$E_c = \eta_o \eta_{st} E_f V_f + E_m V_m \quad (2)$$

This approach is now a standard method for predicting the modulus of short fibre composites, and has been used in this work to model the modulus of Scrimber. Feedlog offcuts, an increment of strands, and two cured beams from a single batch of Scrimber were collected and tested in compression and shear, measured, and examined to provide data for the model. Predictions of the model were then compared with measured Scrimber modulus. This paper is primarily concerned with the estimation of the stress transfer factor η_{st} for the model.

PREVIOUS WORK

Where the wood elements, (in Scrimber these are referred to as strands) are discontinuous, the stress and strain in these strands are not uniform, and it is necessary to characterise the stress transfer into the strands to determine how this affects the modulus of the wood composite. No useful work specifically concerning stress transfer between wood composite elements could be located. However a good model for the transfer of stress between fibres in a short-fibre composite, the “shear-lag” theory, which exists in many forms, was first presented by Cox [2]. His and other variants of the theory are reviewed in Holister and Thomas (Chapter 2) [3]. For this theory it is assumed that: the fibre and matrix are elastic and isotropic; a perfect bond exists between fibre and matrix; there is no load transfer through the ends of the fibre; and fibre shear strain is negligible compared to matrix shear strain.

Consider a tensile load is applied in the fibre longitudinal direction to an idealised composite consisting of aligned short cylindrical fibres, with length L and radius r , in an elastic matrix.

The tensile strain in the composite as a whole, and in the matrix, is considered uniform¹ and called ϵ_c . The shear-lag theory holds that the shear stress on a fibre surface at a point near the end of the fibre varies along the length of the fibre, being directly related to the difference between the fibre tensile strain and the bulk composite tensile strain at each position along the fibre. Cox showed that the tensile stress in the fibre, σ_x , varies along the length of the fibre, L , as:

$$\sigma_x = E_f \epsilon_c \left[1 - \frac{\cosh \omega \left(\frac{L}{2} - x \right)}{\cosh \omega \left(\frac{L}{2} \right)} \right] \quad \omega = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi G_m}{E_f A_f \ln \left(\frac{s}{r} \right)}} \quad (3)$$

- E_f = Fibre modulus in the x direction
 G_m = Matrix shear modulus
 A_f = Fibre cross-sectional area
 s = Mean separation of fibres normal to their length
 r = Fibre radius
 ϵ_c = Matrix strain in the x direction

Fig. 1: Stress profile in a short fibre according to the Cox shear-lag theory

The form of this stress distribution is shown in Figure 1. Cox also showed that the average stress in a fibre is:

$$\sigma_{av} = E_f \epsilon_c \left[1 - \frac{\tanh \left(\frac{\omega L}{2} \right)}{\left(\frac{\omega L}{2} \right)} \right] \quad (4)$$

If the effective modulus of the fibres in the x (longitudinal) direction, E_{eff} , is defined as:

$$E_{eff} = \frac{\sigma_{av}}{\epsilon_c} \quad (5)$$

then the short fibre stress transfer efficiency factor, η_{st} , can be defined as:

$$\eta_{st} = \frac{E_{eff}}{E_f} = \frac{\sigma_{av}}{\sigma_{max}} = 1 - \frac{\tanh \left(\frac{\omega L}{2} \right)}{\left(\frac{\omega L}{2} \right)} \quad (6)$$

¹ A reasonable approximation where the fibre ends of adjacent fibres are evenly distributed along the length of the composite and the fibre cross-sectional area is small compared to the composite cross-sectional area.

Since $\tanh \omega L/2 \approx 1$ where $\omega L/2 > 3$, it can be shown that η_{st} is dependent on ωL . Space does not permit here, but it can be shown also that ωL is related to the "fibre" aspect ratio, L/d , where d is the fibre diameter.

While the shape of the stress transfer profile shown in Figure 1 may well represent the situation in wood composite elements, these equations have been derived assuming a rigid, circular fibre, not a good description of wood composite elements. Another form of the shear-lag theory will now be examined.

For the purposes of investigating the stress transfer mechanism, a wood composite may be thought of as similar to a laminate (like plywood or laminated veneer lumber) made up from discontinuous bonded laminae. The geometry for stress transfer into a lamina in such a laminate is exactly analogous to that for a double lap bonded joint. The pioneering work in this area was done in 1938 by Volkerson, who presented a version of the shear-lag theory suitable for bonded lap-shear joints which is still considered accurate for double-lap joints where adherend bending is not a big factor. This arrangement of the original theory by Volkerson is from Adams and Peppiatt [4]. Figure 2 shows the geometry.

Fig. 2: Geometry of lap joint for Equation 2.10

E and G are the elastic and shear moduli respectively, b is the lap joint width and P is the load on the joint; the subscripts 1, 2, 3 refer to adherend 1, adherend 2, and the adhesive. Volkerson showed that σ_{1x} , the tensile stress on adherend 1, is:

$$\sigma_{1x} = \frac{P}{b\delta_1} \left[1 - \psi (1 - \cosh \alpha x) - \frac{[1 - \psi (1 - \cosh \alpha L)] \sinh \alpha x}{\sinh \alpha L} \right] \quad (7)$$

where:

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{G_3 (E_1 \delta_1 + E_2 \delta_2)}{E_1 E_2 \delta_1 \delta_2 \delta_3}} \quad \psi = \frac{E_2 \delta_2}{E_1 \delta_1 + E_2 \delta_2} \quad (8)$$

The form of the stress profile described by Equation 7 is shown below in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Stress transfer profile in a lap joint

Volkerson's theory is based on the same assumptions as Cox's theory, although of course the assumptions are expressed in terms of the adherends and the adhesive, rather than the fibre and matrix. It can be demonstrated that the right-hand side of the two stress profiles is very similar. The rate of stress build up in a fibre or ply depends on the value of ω or α (in Equation 7 the value of ψ also has a very, very small effect), and for the conditions below Equations 3 and 7 give indistinguishable results to three significant figures. This shows that where stress transfer in a composite can be described by the Volkerson theory, the value of α calculated using this theory could be substituted for ω in Equation 6 to predict η_{st} for the composite.

$$L/2 \leq x \leq L \quad \alpha L > 25 \quad \alpha = \omega \quad \frac{P(1 - \psi)}{b\delta_1} = 2E_f \epsilon_c \quad (9)$$

Three of the assumptions behind the Volkerson theory, namely that the adherend and adhesive remain elastic, that a perfect bond exists between adherend and adhesive, and that there is no load transfer through the ends of the adherend, may be valid for wood composites at low strain. However the assumption that adherend shear strain is negligible compared to adhesive shear strain is clearly invalid, as the shear moduli of wood and adhesive are similar, and the wood element is normally much thicker than the adhesive. Adams and Peppiatt recognised that this is so for many practical lap joints, and presented a modification of the Volkerson theory which incorporates the effect of shear strains in the adherends. In their modified theory, Equation 8 is replaced by:

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{2G_1 G_2 G_3 (E_1 \delta_1 + E_2 \delta_2)}{E_1 \delta_1 E_2 \delta_2 (\delta_1 G_2 G_3 + \delta_2 G_1 G_3 + 2\delta_3 G_1 G_2)}} \quad (10)$$

This equation could be used to calculate the stress transfer profile for wood elements in a wood composite, and thus could be used to estimate η_{st} for a wood composite using Equation 6, rewritten here in terms of α rather than ω :

$$\eta_{st} = 1 - \frac{\tanh\left(\frac{\alpha L}{2}\right)}{\left(\frac{\alpha L}{2}\right)} \quad (11)$$

If Equations 10 and 11 are used to estimate η_{st} for a wood composite, it must be remembered that these equations assume no stress transfer through the ends or the sides of the adherends (wood elements). This assumption will be examined later.

ASPECT RATIO OF SCRIMBER STRANDS

In most short fibre composites and many wood composites the fibre or wood element is an easily identifiable unit with a simple and consistent geometry. The Scrimber strand is a more complex entity, with a large variety of shapes and sizes. One of the first problems in describing Scrimber strands is to decide where one strand ends and the next begins; an increment can contain both independent strands and partially connected clumps. It has been assumed here that the wood in a clump is likely to lie together in the Scrimber, and to transfer stress as a unit. Therefore, for the purposes of stress transfer, a single strand was considered to be any part of the increment which was completely separate from the rest; clumps of partially connected pieces were considered to be a single strand. A representative strand is depicted in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Representative strand shape

The majority of strand ends were of the tapered type. Cracks were a feature of almost every strand, especially the clumps. Many of these cracks may be penetrated by adhesive and bonded during the pressing stage, but others are expected to persist in the cured composite. The presence of unbonded cracks within a strand is expected to lower the rate of stress transfer between strands, but no practical quantitative method of predicting the effect of this on Scrimber modulus could be conceived. Blunt steps were found on only a small minority of strands. Their effect would be the same as that of blunt-ended strands, discussed below, but on a much smaller scale; it was not possible to quantify it.

For stress transfer, it is considered that the most important feature of the strand is whether or not its end is bonded. When a strand end is unbonded, there is no stress transfer through the end, and shear-lag theory can be used to calculate η_{st} for that strand using the strand dimensions. When a strand end is bonded, most of the stress is expected to be transferred through the end. Adhesive bondlines in Scrimber are very thin, with a typical thickness of 0.1mm, and the adhesive modulus E_a is approximately half the strand modulus E_L . Therefore, where strand ends remain bonded, there is no significant variation in the fibre stress near the fibre end, and $\eta_{st} \approx 1$. Since Scrimber made up from end-bonded strands should have the same initial modulus as a hypothetical Scrimber made from continuous strands, for the purpose of calculating η_{st} , end-bonded strands can be considered to have an effectively infinite aspect ratio.

Whether or not a strand end in Scrimber is bonded appears to depend on its degree of taper. During the pressing stage, if the strand has a sufficiently fine taper, adjacent strands are able to deform around the strand end, and to remain in contact with it. This is depicted in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: Effect of strand end shape on end bonding and stress transfer.

Observation of the shapes of voids found at strand ends in Scrimber suggests that, for adjacent strands to be able to deform around the strand end and remain in contact with it, the strand end included angle needs to be less than approximately 30° .

On this basis, the strands in the sample increment were classified according to their end shapes and measured. The great majority of strands had at least one tapered end. Where the strand-end included angle was more than 30° , the end was considered to be blunt, and thus likely to be unbonded if incorporated into Scrimber. Approximately 25% of the strands by weight had two tapered ends. These were assigned an "infinite" aspect ratio, and their total weight fraction only was recorded. For strands with two blunt ends width, thickness, length and weight fraction were recorded. For strands with one blunt end only, the same dimensions were recorded; however in this case an effective length of twice the actual length was assigned and used to calculate an effective aspect ratio.

In total, three sets of data were recorded. In the first data set, as explained above, the actual strand length is recorded for strands with both ends blunt; the effective length for strands with one end blunt, and an "infinite" length for strands with two tapered ends.

A second set of aspect ratio data was recorded to investigate the effect on predicted Scrimber modulus of all strand ends being considered unbonded. In this set, the actual strand length was recorded for strands with one and both ends blunt. Since individual measurements had not been taken of strands with both ends tapered, these were excluded from this data set, which was recorded as a crude type of worst-case.

It was necessary to record a third aspect ratio data set because of a manufacturing practise at Scrimber International. The most common reason for strands having a blunt end was that this end was part of the original guillotined log end. These guillotined blunt ends were found close to the increment ends, which placed them on the surface of the cured beam. Since the average thickness of an increment after pressing was 5.5 mm, most of these blunt ends were found within that distance of the surface of the cured beam. It was regular Scrimber International practise to plane some material from all surfaces of the beam before use, and accordingly approximately 7mm was planed from the surface of beams 2270/4 and 2270/5 during production of the compression specimens. The compression specimens tested in this work therefore included few guillotined ends, and their modulus could be expected to reflect this.

For the third set of aspect ratio data, strands with the guillotined blunt end were re-evaluated, and considered to have a tapered end in its place, since those strands, after incorporation in the Scrimber beam, would have gained a tapered end during planing. Strand effective lengths

were modified accordingly. This third set of aspect ratio data is considered to be the most representative of the strands making up the compression specimens for Scrimber batch 2270.

VERIFICATION OF THE SHEAR-LAG THEORY FOR WOOD COMPOSITES

To verify that the shear-lag theory as developed by Adams and Peppiatt [4] for non-rigid adherends adequately predicts stress transfer in wood composites, the predictions of that theory were tested against strain measurements near the end of a wood element in a simple wood composite. Laminated Veneer Lumber (LVL), was chosen as a suitable composite because it has a simple and consistent wood element geometry and similar glue-lines to Scrimber. Most importantly, the stress state within a loaded section of LVL was expected to be more predictable than in other wood composites, especially Scrimber, and the wood elements within LVL were large enough to easily apply bonded foil strain-gauges.

The LVL chosen was made up from 15 rotary-peeled 3mm plies of Radiata, from the same general area as the Scrimber feedlogs. The plies, each 1200 mm long, were bonded with phenol formaldehyde adhesive; the outer three plies on each face were scarf jointed, while the remainder were laid butt to butt with a small gap, typically 1 mm. The longitudinal direction of each ply coincided with the longitudinal direction of the specimen.

A 600mm long piece of LVL was cut as a test piece. The test specimen was 47mm thick (normal to the ply plane) and 10mm deep. A ply end near the centre of the test specimen, in an area generally free from other butt joints or grain irregularities, was chosen for measurement of the strain build-up. Foil strain gauges were bonded to the edge of the ply near its end. The gap between the two ply ends was 1mm; approximately 70% of the gap was filled with adhesive spew incorporating bubbles. Stress transfer in the LVL test specimen was expected to be similar to that in a double-lap-shear specimen. The geometry of the test specimen, considered as a double lap-shear specimen and using the notation of Adams and Peppiatt from Figure 2, is set out in Figure 6.

Figure 6. LVL considered as a double lap shear specimen.

The stress transfer Equation 7 from Adams and Peppiatt has been rewritten in terms of the notation in Figure 6. It predicts that for $0 \leq x < L/2$:

$$\sigma_{2x} = \frac{F}{2\delta_2 b} \left[\psi (1 - \cosh \alpha x) + \frac{[1 - \psi (1 - \cosh \alpha L)] \sinh \alpha x}{\sinh \alpha L} \right] \quad (12)$$

where (Eqn 10):

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{2G_1 G_2 G_3 (E_1 \delta_1 + E_2 \delta_2)}{E_1 \delta_1 E_2 \delta_2 (\delta_1 G_2 G_3 + \delta_2 G_1 G_3 + 2\delta_3 G_1 G_2)}}$$

A modification must be made to Equation 10 in order to predict a sensible value of α for the LVL experimental configuration. Equation 10 is based on the assumption that both adherends are free to deform in shear. Since the gap between the ply ends is very small, adherend 1 is effectively rigid, and $G_1 \gg G_2$. In addition, because the adhesive is very thin, $\delta_2 G_3 \gg 2\delta_3 G_2$, and in this case $E_1 = E_2$. Therefore the equation can be simplified to:

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{2G_2 (\delta_1 + \delta_2)}{E_1 \delta_1 \delta_2^2}} \quad (13)$$

Using Equation 13, α was calculated for the LVL experimental configuration shown in Figure 6. The predicted value of α for the LVL specimen was 0.26. The strain-gauged LVL specimen was loaded in tension to 20 kN, in 1 kN steps. At each step, individual gauge readings were recorded. All strain/load plots were linear for specimen loads up to 8 kN. For this initial linear section, Figure 7 shows the relative strain in the ply under each of the strain gauges plotted against the distance of the gauge from the ply end.

Extrapolation of the measured strain profile to the ply end indicates that the strain at the ply end was approximately 50% of the maximum ply strain; ie. roughly 50% of the load was transferred into the ply through its end. This load is thought to have been transferred by tensile stresses in the adhesive spew, which as noted previously filled approximately 70% of the inter-ply gap. In addition, the measured rate of strain transfer (controlled by the value of α in the shear-lag model) for the ply is less than predicted, and therefore the predicted value of α appears to have been too high. The rate of stress transfer into the ply could be expected to have been reduced by the peeling cracks observed in every ply. The presence of these cracks apparently lowers the ply shear stiffness G_2 and consequently α has been overestimated.

A shear lag profile can be shown to closely fit the measured strain transfer profile if $\alpha = 0.15$ and $\sigma = 0$ at $x = -4.5$ mm (which corresponds to the strain at the ply end being 52% of the maximum strain), as demonstrated in Figure 7. This suggests that the chosen shear-lag theory can accurately predict the form of the stress transfer profile in a wood element if the amount of stress transferred through the end is known and the effect of wood element internal cracking on the effective shear modulus of the wood element can be estimated.

Figure 7. Fitting of the shear-lag prediction to the measured strain profile.

It must be emphasised that the stress transfer profile described above applied only where specimen load was less than 8kN. The strain gauge measurements also indicated partial failures of the ply end bond at 8kN and again at 15kN. The strain transfer profiles above these loads showed progressively less strain transfer through the end of the ply.

This experiment confirmed that the stress profile in a wood composite element fits the shear-lag form very well, and that the appropriate shear-lag theory can be used to predict η_{st} for wood composites. It also showed that estimates of α , and therefore η_{st} , however, from wood element geometry and properties are likely to be too high if the wood element contains internal unbonded cracks. A porous spew fillet 1mm thick, bonding approximately 70% of the strand end surface, was apparently able to transfer 52% of maximum ply stress through a very blunt ply end. The result suggests that, in a lightly-loaded wood composite, for a wood element with a well-bonded end, almost all of the stress could be expected to be carried through the end. This justifies the proposal made earlier that end-bonded strands could be treated as effectively continuous for the estimation of η_{st} .

ESTIMATION OF THE STRESS TRANSFER FACTOR FOR SCRIMBER

In detailed investigations of the microstructure of Scrimber it was found that the strand cross-section circumference was similar to that of a square of the same area, and that at least 40% of the strand surface was unbonded. Therefore for the purposes of predicting stress transfer between strands in Scrimber, the typical strand was assumed to be square in cross-section, and bonded on two opposite sides only. (The unbonded surface fraction was thus assumed to be 50%.) The strand was also assumed to be in the centre of the Scrimber compression specimen, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Geometry and notation for application of shear-lag theory to Scrimber.

The notation used is the same as for the LVL specimen in Figure 6. The strand cross-sectional dimensions were calculated as shown below, where A_s is the measured strand cross-section area and D_s is the batch 2270 densification factor:

$$2\delta_2 = \sqrt{\frac{A_s}{D_s}} \quad (14)$$

For each strand, the variable $\alpha_{(i)}$ was calculated from Equation 13 and the stress transfer efficiency factor, $\eta_{st(i)}$, was then calculated from Equation 11. $P_{(i)}$ was defined as the strand mass divided by the sample mass. For Scrimber batch 2270, η_{st} was calculated for each set of strand aspect ratio measurements using:

$$\eta_{st} = \sum_{i=0}^{i=n} \eta_{st(i)} P_{(i)} \quad (15)$$

For Set 3, believed to be the most representative set of aspect ratio measurements for the sample increment, η_{st} was calculated to be 0.98. For Set 1 (not corrected for the absence of guillotined ends in the Scrimber specimens) $\eta_{st} = 0.96$; and for Set 2 (the crude worst case), $\eta_{st} = 0.94$.

The estimate of $\eta_{st} = 0.98$ for batch 2270 reached above is probably too high, as it relies on the assumption that the Scrimber strands were internally intact. However investigations of Scrimber microstructure found that internal unbonded cracks were likely to be present in the majority of strands. No practical method of predicting the effect of these internal cracks could be conceived. The quantitative effect of these cracks can only be guessed, using the LVL stress transfer experiment as a guide. Given that relatively minor internal cracking lowered the effective value of α in the LVL to 60% of the predicted value, it seems possible that the existence of cracks within the majority of Scrimber strands might reduce the effective value of α for those strands to half or even a third of its predicted value, giving rise to an estimate for η_{st} as low as 0.95.

MODEL PREDICTIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The Krenchel-type model introduced in as Equation 2 was found to need modification as follows. The symbols are defined below.

$$E_s = \eta_d D_s E_w \quad (16)$$

This makes the full model:

$$E_B (\text{Scrimber}) = \eta_{st} \eta_o (\eta_d D_s E_w) V_s + E_a V_a \quad (17)$$

Values for all the variables in this relationship were found for Scrimber batch 2270. Using this proposed model, the average modulus of the Scrimber batch 2270 compression specimens was predicted to be 11.05 GPa at standard conditions. This compares well with the average measured modulus for those specimens of 10.8 GPa at standard conditions.

η_{st} (stress transfer efficiency factor)	= 0.98.	E_w (feedlog modulus)	= 12.9 GPa.
η_o (orientation efficiency factor)	= 0.875.	V_s (strand volume fraction)	= 0.875.
η_d (strand damage factor)	= 0.88.	E_a (adhesive modulus)	= 7.6 GPa.
D_s (strand densification factor)	= 1.27.	V_a (adhesive volume fraction)	= 0.03.

Although it was impractical to attempt to design an experiment to test the effect of strand aspect ratio, and therefore stress transfer, directly, the apparent accuracy of the whole model allows some confidence in the predicted value of the various factors.

Strand discontinuity was found to have only a small effect on Scrimber modulus. The high strand unbonded surface fraction of the batch studied also had little effect on modulus. Strand misorientation and damage were found to be the major factors reducing Scrimber modulus.

This method described here of estimating the effect of "fibre" discontinuity in wood composites is relatively simple and demonstrates the usefulness of applying standard composites theory, allied with a good grasp of the composite microstructure, to the modelling of wood composites. Procedures for estimating the efficiency factors could easily be modified for application to other wood composites.

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